

Phases of Risk Management for the James Webb Space Telescope

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Abstract—The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)^{1,2} mission will launch a 6-meter class infrared telescope to L2 in 2010 to study the earliest stars and galaxies formed after the “Big Bang.” JWST has been designated as the highest priority mission in space astronomy by the National Academy of Sciences. As the JWST Project moves from conceptual stage through the formulation, design, and development phases and into the operational phase, the risk management emphasis and philosophy will also change. During the formulation phase, the JWST Project has exercised a top-down risk mitigation philosophy which has greatly reduced mission risk by investing significantly in a number of key technologies required for the observatory, including cryogenic and deployable lightweight mirrors, precision actuators, infrared detectors and techniques for Wavefront sensing and control. As the project moves into implementation phase, we have initiated the use of a more formal, bottom-up risk management methodology. This paper discusses the:

- Two phases of risk management philosophy for the JWST program
- Process of developing a web-based risk database tool
- Policies and procedures in use for conducting risk management across the boundaries with a number of partners (including the prime contractor, European Space Agency, Canadian Space Agency and the Space Telescope Science Institute)
- Management approaches which have been devised to address communicating and managing risks across a large, diverse, and multi-level organization.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Even with its new instruments, the observations of the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) are limited to “adolescent” objects. The younger objects from the first billion years after the “Big Bang,” the period when galaxies were formed, are receding from Earth at a fast rate and are red-shifted into the near infrared (past 2 microns) where HST loses sensitivity.

To peer into this period of the evolution of the universe, NASA will develop, launch, and operate a state-of-the-art space-based observatory as a follow-on mission to HST. This telescope will allow scientists to see the first generations of stars. This observatory, with its large, light-gathering mirror, will have superb resolution, capable of detecting faint signals. This observatory is named the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) after NASA’s second administrator, a man of great vision.

A preliminary concept for JWST is shown in Figure 1.

¹ U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright

² IEEEAC Paper No. 1292

Figure 1 – JWST Preliminary Concept

Technological Challenge

In order to achieve its objectives, JWST will require several new technologies:

- To observe in infrared wavelength, a tennis court-sized deployable sunshield will be developed to allow the telescope to cool down to cryogenic temperature.
- Compared to HST, JWST will fly a significantly larger mirror, which will also be considerably lighter and foldable to allow the observatory to be compatible with the volume and lift capability of existing launch vehicles.
- The mirror figure will be adjustable on orbit to correct for the residual errors after mirror deployment and errors introduced due to variations in the thermal environment during operation.
- Wavefront Sensing and Control (WFS&C) algorithms will be developed to sense the errors in mirror shape and determine the solution that fixes the error.
- Cryogenic mechanisms with extremely fine position control (~10 nm step size) will be required for primary mirror segment figure control.
- New focal plane technology will be required to enable the development of high-sensitivity, large-format instruments that, together with the large, low-temperature optical telescope, will provide the capability necessary to complete the science mission. Required characteristics of the detector systems include low-noise near- and mid-infrared detectors, Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) and ultra-low background detector evaluation facilities.
- A programmable aperture mask using Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) will be required to improve the observation efficiency of the telescope so it can complete its mission within its the design lifetime. MEMS will significantly enhance the capability of the Near-Infrared Spectrometer (NIRSpec) to measure many hundreds of spectra per observation and provide a high degree of parallelism to significantly enhance operability and robustness

Organizational Challenge

Numerous organizations will take part in the development of this observatory. NASA, Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) is in charge of the overall mission. TRW, as the prime contractor for this endeavor, is responsible for building the Optical Telescope Element and the spacecraft and is responsible for system level integration and testing of the Observatory. The University of Arizona, teaming with Lockheed Martin, is to develop the Near Infrared Camera (NIRCam), one of the scientific instruments. The European Space Agency (ESA), teaming with European industry, is to develop Near-Infrared Spectrometer and make significant contribution to the development of the Mid-Infrared Instrument (MIRI). ESA is also to make a yet-to-be-determined contribution towards a non-instrument aspect of the observatory. The Canadian Space Agency is to develop the Fine Guidance Sensors for the observatory pointing control. Space Telescope Science Institute is responsible for developing the ground system for flight operations.

Coordination between all national and international organizations and developing and maintaining proper interfaces between them poses a formidable challenge to project management and the systems engineering group.

At the time of this writing, JWST is at the end of the formulation phase and is in the process of entering the implementation phase. Accordingly, this paper is divided into two parts. The first part describes risk management activities employed during formulation phase where specific risks have been identified, mitigation plans have been defined, and resources have been committed to mitigate these risks. The second part of this paper discusses the activities undertaken by the project to prepare for the classical risk mitigation process for identifying, analyzing and tracking risks during implementation phases. No specific risks are discussed in the second part of this paper.

2. RISK MANAGEMENT IN FORMULATION PHASE

Risk management during the early (formulation) phase of this project is driven from a top-down perspective where a "Risk Watch List" dictates risk mitigation activities for the project. Some examples of the top-down risks include:

- Available funding profile may not match schedule needs
- System complexity, number and variety of partners, and interfaces in a highly interdependent cross-coupled system
- Fabrication and test of all optics
- Deployable sunshield thermal performance
- Ground-based performance verification (optical, thermal, mechanical, line of sight stability, etc.)
- Availability of mid-sized Evolved Expendable Launch Vehicle (EELV)
- Detector development schedule

The key focus of the risk management team in this stage of the project is concerned with:

- Making sure the right technologies are developed in a timely manner.
- Conducting cost to benefit trades of the observatory architecture and design requirements.
- Establishing and maintaining appropriate technical, cost, and schedule margin requirements to guide the design of the observatory during the detailed design phase.

Figure 2 depicts the essence of this approach.

Figure 2 – Risk Mitigation during Phase A

Technology Development

A major decision regarding technology development has been whether the government or the prime contractor would develop new technologies. Continuous review of requirements and progress against those requirements, as well as identifying the risks involved, are key factors in managing the risks associated with technology development. Communication is also crucial, to keep contractors informed of government-funded technology programs and to have government involvement in contractor-led activities. Technology development activities are divided as follows:

- Optics are being developed within government programs in order to split the choice of contractor/architecture from the specifics of the primary mirror technology and the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the optics.
- Due to their level of expertise and the fact that solutions are architecture-dependent, the contractor is developing deployable systems and the sunshield. This also makes optimal use of the independent research and development (IR&D) investment.
- Detectors and MEMS are being developed within government programs in order to most efficiently fund multiple vendors and provide detectors to all the science instruments.

To further reduce the risk of the technology development program, multiple teams are chartered to develop the same technology. This competitive environment also increases the chances for a superior technology to emerge.

The multiple development approach for JWST technologies is described below.

Architecture Studies—Two leading aerospace companies, (Lockheed Martin and TRW) were chosen through competitive selection to conduct Phase-A studies and develop independent architectures for JWST. Preliminary concepts developed by the two teams are shown in Figures 3 and 4. The TRW concept has now been selected to be carried through the detailed design and development phase.

Figure 3 – TRW Preliminary Concept

Figure 4 – Lockheed Martin Preliminary Concept

Primary Mirror—The Advanced Mirror Systems Demonstrator (AMSD) program chartered three vendors to develop lightweight mirrors that will meet the requirements for this mission. Clear objectives and test demonstration requirements have been laid out for all three vendors so that a final selection of the flight mirrors can be made objectively.

Infrared Detectors—The detector development program has selected two vendors to develop detectors that could meet JWST requirements. Each vendor is also producing detailed costing studies so that all parameters affecting detector costs can be clearly understood before selecting the detector for the Observatory.

MEMS—Three teams had been competing to develop the programmable aperture mask for the observatory using

MEMS technology. The three teams investigated two different MEMS technologies, micro-shutters and micro mirrors, for this application. As of this writing, the project has already selected the team that will develop the flight MEMS with micro-shutter technology.

WFS&C—A government sponsored team, led by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), as well as the two Phase-A study teams, TRW and Lockheed, had been independently developing this technology. During Phase B, TRW has been selected as the sole Phase B/C/D prime contractor leaving two teams to continue this work. NASA will soon make the decision on whether to continue the dual development or combine the resources as a single concentrated effort to mature this technology to a flight-worthy level.

Science Instruments—JWST international partners have also embarked on a similar risk management approach for developing their instruments by chartering two different contractors to conduct four feasibility studies for NIRSPEC, the recipient of MEMS technology. There are four funded configurations – two MEMS solutions and two non-MEMS solutions.

All major enabling technologies for the JWST mission have been demonstrated at the brass board level. Detailed development plans with intermediate, measurable milestones are in process towards the production of flight prototypes by the Non Advocate Review, the gateway review before initiating the implementation phase.

Cost-to-Benefit Trade Studies

As the results of Phase-A studies and technology development activities provided insight into the challenges ahead, the JWST project conducted trade studies to evaluate design requirements against risk, cost, and schedule. The project concluded that some requirements could be relaxed to gain considerable risk margins. Some examples of scope of requirements are listed below:

Primary Mirror Size—Reducing the primary mirror size from an 8-meter class to a 6-meter class reduced the schedule risk for constructing, grinding and polishing the mirror.

Mirror thickness—Weight savings from reduction in mirror diameter was invested in increasing the mirror areal density from 15 kg/m² to 20 kg/m². A sturdier mirror will reduce gravity effects during ground processing, greatly enhancing ground testability. A thicker mirror will also increase the opto-thermal stability of the mirror against fluctuations of the on-orbit environment, reducing the frequency of adjustment to the mirror shape during on orbit operation.

Minimum Design Margins

System design options for JWST are required to show appropriate margins for all critical resources allocated to each subsystem, as defined below:

- Power > 30%
- Mass > 30%
- Thermal > 50% (parasitic load capability)
- Cost > 35% Contingency
- Schedule > 1 month/year of the implementation phase

These margins will minimize the impact of unpredictable problems that may arise during the course of the project.

3. RISK MANAGEMENT IN PHASE B AND BEYOND

With the initiation of the detailed design and implementation phase, a more formal and structured risk management process is necessary. This requires establishing the Risk Management Board, developing a formal risk management plan, and developing or procuring a risk management tool that allows us to proactively and effectively communicate and manage risks across a large, diverse, and multi-level organization.

Risk Management Tool

A tiger team was established to prepare a Continuous Risk Management (CRM) Plan, perform a requirements definition for the risk management tool, develop the required tools, and train project personnel in risk management and use of the tool.

The tiger team established the following requirements for the risk management process and for the tools to facilitate this process:

- Information must be internally consistent and changes must be tracked effectively.
- Adequate information must be available for each risk such that an individual not directly connected with its original formulation can gain sufficient understanding of its origin and consequences so as to be able to participate in its resolution.
- Risk information is secure from unauthorized alteration, damage or loss, and from exposure to unauthorized individuals.
- Data elements that are subject to be modified by particular individuals must be clear.
- Reports are consistent, self-explanatory, and tailored to the needs of the users.
- Risk information is accessible to all stakeholders through a web interface.
- Data entry of new information is easy and straightforward, with an easy-to-learn user interface.
- Status of a risk at any point in time must be unambiguous.
- Priority information must be directly connected to the other risk elements.

To assist in the Risk Management Tool (RMT) development phase, the risk team evaluated other risk management databases used at GSFC and across other NASA facilities, as well as commercially available tools. No single system met all the requirements listed above, so it was decided that the most advantageous approach was to select the best features from many of the systems studied and implement them into our own system, taking advantage of the JWST web site with existing functional applications, such as security, e-mail notifications, and other aspects that were also required. Other advantages of building a custom Risk

Management module for our internal website included a smaller learning curve, accessibility, programmability, timeliness of development, and the ability to provide users with an intuitive tool that could be upgraded as required to meet future needs.

A fully functional risk management tool was up and running within three months. The RMT has been designed and implemented so that all users of the system can gain familiarity with it, and trust its contents and integrity in a short initial period of use. The Risk Database, to be used effectively, must play the role of a simple, transparent utility to all users including the front-line workers and management.

RMT Characteristics—the user interface screens shown in Figures 5 and 6 best describe key characteristics and capabilities of the RMT.

Figure 5 – View Risk Screen

Figure 6 – Risk History Screen

The RMT is a web-based tool for capturing, recording, and distributing information about risks. Each risk is automatically assigned a unique identifier and stored in a common database. Risks are classified according to their selected likelihood, cost impact, schedule impact and technical impact. The tool computes a risk exposure level from these inputs. Users can add, edit, view, select, and list risks. They can also get tabular, metric, and graphical reports.

In determining the risk exposure level, the tool provides clear guidelines on how to categorize the cost, schedule and technical impacts.

Since the RMT is an integral part of the JWST internal web site, access to risk-related information can be easily controlled using the access control mechanism of this web site. In this mechanism, each user is assigned to a specific user class and each user class has a pre-defined authority to access the types of information. This way, if necessary, proprietary data or sensitive financial data is viewable by only those users authorized to see it.

Risk Management Mechanics

When a risk is submitted, it is automatically given a status of “New”. The submitter is required to identify (from a ‘pick list’) the group that in the submitter’s judgment needs to address the risk. While the status is “New”, the Originator, Submitter, Responsible Group Lead, and Responsible Group Risk Coordinator can view and edit the risk. When someone other than the Originator or Submitter edits the risk, the status is changed to “Open”. Once the status is “Open”, only the Group Lead, Group Risk Coordinator, and the Assignee can make changes to the risk. The system will notify the Submitter, Lead, and the Risk Coordinator if the responsible parties have not viewed the “New” risk within seven calendar days of being submitted.

The Group Lead (or Coordinator) is then responsible for determining whether their group is the appropriate one to address the submitted risk and if so, assigning the risk to an individual within that group. The system will notify the “assignee” that a risk has been assigned. The Assignee, Group Lead, or Coordinator evaluates the risk and ranks it according to Likelihood, Technical, Cost, and Schedule consequences. The Group Lead or a subsystem/component manager within that group is then held responsible to assess, mitigate, and track the risks within their control.

If necessary, the Group Lead or coordinator can reassign the “New” risk to another group that is more appropriate to deal with the submitted risk. The coordinator of the new group will receive e-mail notification of that action. Once the risk has been reassigned the old Group Lead cannot make any changes to the risk.

After the initial definitions are set in place, the process of working the risk is set in motion. Analyses and progress are documented in the RMT. Project Managers can monitor the changing status of any risk using this on-line system.

Organizational Structure for Risk Management

The project organization has been structured to be conducive to CRM for the remaining program phases. Key aspects of the organization are described below.

- The Risk Management Board (RMB) consists of senior management and systems engineering personnel.
- Systems engineering process crosses all product boundaries.
- All domestic and international partners are members of the Systems Engineering Board.
- Senior managers from the US and international partners are members of the Senior Leadership Team, supporting the JWST Project Manager.
- Experienced Product Integrity Teams serve as advisers for project management.
- Risk management trigger-points are tracked in the project schedules.
- Budget liens are identified for risk mitigation plans.

The RMB consists of the Deputy Project Manager, the Deputy Project Manager for Resources, the senior Project Scientist, senior managers representing major elements of the observatory, representatives from international partners, the Risk Coordinator, System Assurance Manager, and the Chief Systems Engineer. The Project Manager serves as an *ex-officio* member of the RMB and has final authority on risk management aspects.

The RMB has oversight responsibility for the entire risk process. The board reviews risk identification and analysis data, as well as action plans. The board conducts the risk control function by which they review the present allocation of resources to risk action activities and consider whether to change that allocation as a function of time.

The Risk Coordinator supports the RMB by ensuring that the overall risk process continues smoothly and that all required data are collected and placed in the database in a timely manner. The Risk Coordinator also provides all levels of training. Some of the responsibilities of the Risk Coordinator include:

- Serves as the Secretary to the RMB
- Manages the Project Risk Database
- Coordinates the risk process with risk and reliability professionals at GSFC and NASA-wide
- Serves as an *ex-officio* member of each team by attending meetings as a representative of the Project RMB.
- Responsible for training project users

The Risk Coordinator also chairs the Risk Working Group (RWG) that meets as needed. The RWG membership is open to any member of the larger team who is interested in the details of a specific risk.

The members of individual teams provide the expertise for identifying and assessing individual risks as they are initiated and moved through the system.

The critical expertise for risk identification, analysis, and action planning lies with the JWST team as a whole and

each individual team member operating within their specific discipline and local team affiliation(s). Risks are identified first at the team level and it is at this level that the best estimates of probability of occurrence and impact can be determined. It is the members of the team who will have the detailed context knowledge to be able to suggest risk mitigations or other forms of addressing specific risks.

Each team has the flexibility to organize its risk management activities as it chooses. However, for purposes of standard communication outside the individual teams, the use of common rating scales for probability and impact, and the use of the Project Risk Database to document the risks, is required.

The Systems Engineering Team (SET) plays a critical role in our risk management. The SET is responsible for:

- Maintaining the configured requirements for the Project.
- Performing trade studies of alternate technologies and their associated performance parameters.
- Providing discipline engineers to assist in the review, interpretation, and detailed planning for risk mitigations.
- Planning and managing reserves at the System, Segment, and Subsystem level for mass, power, volume, and other parameters.
- Assigning a lead Systems Engineer to each Segment and Element (and also lower level subsystems as required).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The JWST project is in the process of transitioning from formulation phase to the implementation phase. A top-down risk management process during the formulation phase has successfully reduced the risks associated with developing the technologies necessary to achieve the scientific goals of this mission. Several steps have been undertaken in preparation for the detail design and implementation phases of the mission. An organizational structure has been put in place that will allow easy communication between all partners and properly manage all technical and management interfaces. Clear roles and responsibilities have been defined for aggressive risk management at all levels within the project.

In preparation for the detailed design and development phases of the project, a formal risk management process has been established that allows a bottom-up approach to risk management. A web-based Risk Management Tool has been developed that will allow all U.S. and international partners to communicate risk information in a consistent and timely manner. The project team has received formal training in risk management and the utilization of the RMT.

The project is now ready with a comprehensive set of risk management capabilities to take on the challenges ahead during the design, implementation and eventually operational phases of this remarkable scientific mission.

5. REFERENCES

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6. BIOGRAPHIES

Mansoor Ahmed – Mr. Ahmed received his Masters degree in Mechanical Engineering from George Washington University in 1980. He has been a part of the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) program since 1982 when he lead the HST thermal engineering team during the design phase of HST. He continued in this role through the first servicing mission for HST. He supported the preparations for the second servicing mission as a systems engineer for development of replacement hardware for HST and was part of the anomaly resolution team during the mission. After the second servicing mission, Mr. Ahmed served as the Flight Operations Manager for HST, responsible for day-to-day operations of the telescope. Mr. Ahmed was named to Mission Manager for the Compton Gamma Ray Observatory Re-entry mission, which was successfully concluded in June 2000. He is currently serving as the deputy project manager for the James Webb Space Telescope.

Steven Brill – a graduate of Rollins College, Florida, Mr. Brill has been involved in risk management in both the DOD and aerospace industries for 30 years. His first introduction to risk management was while serving with the U.S. Air Force. He then worked for Harris Corporation for 8 years, Martin Marietta for 13 years, and has been a contractor at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center for nearly 10 years. He is currently working on the James Webb Space Telescope Project as a Management Planner for the Integrated Science Instrument Module and also provides planning support to NASA HQ's Office of Space Science.

Jonathan Bryson – Mr. Bryson is the Deputy Project Manager-Resources for the James Webb Space Telescope Project. He has a Masters degree in Public Administration from the Maxwell School, Syracuse University and an MS degree in Computer Systems Management from the University of Maryland. Mr. Bryson has over a decade of resources management

experience for NASA flight projects including the Hubble Space Telescope and Earth Observing System (EOS) Terra missions.

Ratna Sengupta –Ms. Sengupta received her B.Sc. degree in Physics in India, and her BS in Computer Science and MS in Computer Systems Management from the University of Maryland. She worked at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration before joining the Flight Software group for the Hubble Space Telescope as a Test Engineer. She actively supported two servicing missions for HST and saw through all the phases of replacing the on-board computer. Currently she is serving as the Risk Coordinator for the James Webb Space Telescope and also works with the Optical Modeling group.

Leonard Olson (photo not available) – Mr. Olson received his Ph.D. in Physics from Virginia Polytechnic and State University before coming to work at GSFC as a contractor in 1980. In 1985 he joined Raytheon and began support of the Cosmic Background Explorer (COBE) Project. From 1992-2001, he supported the HST Program at GSFC in a variety of capacities. From December 2001 to August 2002 he served as the Risk Coordinator for the JWST. He is currently a Technical Area Lead supporting the QSS Group, Inc. Computational Sciences Research and Development Services contract for Division IC at Ames Research Center in California.